

Ozone (2B) Instrument Description

Last updated 20 Jan 2026

Ozone measurements are made by the FAAM Airborne Laboratory using a dual beam UV absorption photometer, specifically a 2B Technologies model 205 (rackmount, s/n 1034DB). This instrument has been flown since 2011, and is operated as shown in the flow diagram below.

Following recommendations from 2B Technologies to improve precision for 2 sec data acquisition rates, the photometer motherboard and firmware were upgraded to version 'I' and a new UV lamp block fitted in Oct 2020.

The instrument sample flow rate is approximately 2.5 SLPM, provided by its internal sampling pump.

An 5 μm PTFE particulate membrane, held in an external in-line PFA filter holder (Entegris part no. 411-4), protects the photometer's internal optics from potential contamination.

Note that the I/Io cell measurement cycle is 2 sec; although data submitted in the core_faam_yyyyymmdd_v00x_rx_cxxx_1hz.nc data files is logged at 1 Hz, the true measurement rate is ~ 0.5 Hz.

Aircraft sample inlet and instrument response

From 2012 to 2021, a rear-ward facing ½" OD stainless steel (SS) tube, mounted on a blank BAe-146 aircraft Aluminium window, served as an ozone inlet. The SS tube ID was lined with a ⅜" OD PFA Teflon tube, to accommodate simultaneous atmospheric sampling of ozone, sulphur dioxide and carbon monoxide.

Since 2021, a new pressure-building trace gas inlet has replaced the rear-ward facing inlet. This inlet was initially designed by Richard J. McLaughlin, an instrument design and fabrication specialist at NOAA's Chemical Sciences Division, for NASA's Douglas DC8 (e.g. ATom-2 missions) and NOAA's Lockheed WP-3D Orion aircrafts. The inlet design was first adapted to interface with our aircraft windows by Chris Reed at FAAM in 2019, for use as a fast NOx measurements inlet.

The new core chemistry McLaughlin inlet is located on starboard windows no. 11 or 12 depending on the cabin configuration (i.e. ~12 to 13 m from the nose of the aircraft). The picture below illustrates the pylon/shroud inlet mounted on window no. 11 (nose of aircraft to the RHS of picture).

Two of the three inlet internal ports within the pylon are lined with 1/4" OD PFA Teflon tubes, then teed to a single 3/8" OD PFA Teflon tube.

Ambient air is drawn into the aircraft cabin through the ⅜" OD Teflon tube using an all-PTFE Teflon double-headed sample pump (KNF part no. N834.3 FTE). The sample flow (~25 SLPM near surface, degrading to ~ 7 SLPM at 35000') passes through a two-way, normally open, electro-solenoid all-PFA valve (eValve5, Entegris/Galtek part no. 203-2414-213), used to seal the inlet during pre-flight preparations.

The operation of the KNF sample pump and eValve 5 is automated by the aircraft weight-on-wheels signal; ambient air sampling starts as soon as the aircraft is airborne. This

arrangement minimises instrument inlet contamination by airfield polluted air, such as during engines start with aircraft parked on stand, or while taxiing for take-off and after landing.

The air sample is transferred to a 3/8" to 1/4" Teflon tee piece (Entegris/Galtek part no part# UT4-6-4N); a short length 1/4" od Teflon tubing connects the tee piece to the ozone instrument inlet particulate filter.

The excess flow provided by the KNF sample pump is directed to a PFA Teflon buffer volume (PFAVOL) constructed out of three 1 1/2" MNPT 120 mL column segments (Savillex part no. 500-120-02), 3/8" OD tube port closures (Savillex part no. 600-058-19), and female connectors (Savillex part no. 730-0502). The buffer volume is used to dampen oscillating flow effects caused by the KNF sample pump (double diaphragm pressure pulses).

An ozone instrument zero can be performed pre- and post-flight using an external 500 mL capacity scrubber cartridge (Cole Parmer part no. 01418-50) equipped with in-line PFA filter holder (Entegris part no. 411-4) and 5 μ m PTFE membrane. This scrubber cartridge is half-filled with potassium permanganate coated alumina spheres (Sofnofil, from Molecular Products Ltd), and activated charcoal, for the removal of NO_x, Ozone and SO₂. During the preparatory phase on the ground, the KNF sample pump is powered off, cabin air can pass through this scrubber cartridge by actuating the three-way electro-solenoid eValve 6 (Entegris/Galtek part no. 203-3414-213), so ozone-scrubbed cabin air can be sampled by the ozone photometer.

During flight, the overflow from the KNF sample pump is constantly monitored by a microbridge mass airflow sensor (MFM, Honeywell model AWM5104VN, 0-20 SLPM), to ensure cabin air is not inadvertently sampled, especially when the inlet pumping performance decreases while approaching our flight ceiling altitude (30000-35000 feet).

The above sampling inlet arrangement enables the ozone photometer to work within its operating pressure limits, with its inlet pressure effectively following the aircraft cabin pressure.

Based on the current inlet configuration, the instrument lag time is estimated to be $\sim 2 \pm 1$ sec based on comparison of 1 Hz ozone and 10 Hz nitric oxide measurements (ozone titration assessment in ship plumes during the ACRUISE1 2019 missions). Please note that no correction for lag time has been applied to our submitted data timestamps.

Calibration and measurement traceability

FAAM's ozone photometer model 205 is calibrated at least yearly against an ozone primary standard (Thermo Scientific model 49i-PS, s/n 0703820527) maintained by the University of York's [COZI laboratory](#), part of the Wolfson Atmospheric Chemistry Laboratories. This primary standard ensures the traceability of ozone photometers operated by ground-based and airborne facilities of the National Centre for Atmospheric Science to NIST/NPL.

FAAM's ozone photometers are generally calibrated over the range 0-500 ppb, to cover the high ozone concentrations encountered at high altitudes in stratospheric influenced air.

The photometer is "zeroed" during pre-flights (see previous section) to check the ozone measurements comply with the expected instrumental precision (<1 ppb for 10 second averages).

FAAM operates an ozone calibration source (2B Technologies model 306, s/n 238). This calibration source is calibrated against the COZI laboratory ozone primary standard using 2B Technologies' Technical Note No 016 (https://2btech.io/wp-content/uploads/docs/tech_notes/TN016.pdf).

Measurement uncertainty

The uncertainty of ozone measurements can be estimated from the calibration of FAAM's ozone calibration source, namely for amount fractions greater than 100 nmol/mol: $\pm 3\%$ of value, and for amount fractions between 0 and 100 nmol/mol: ± 3 nmol/mol.

A further source of uncertainty was quantified after 2019 missions and reported in FAAM's placement student Jake Vallow's Master of Chemistry thesis (April 2021). This FAAM study of the impact of water vapour and pressure on the accuracy of our model 205 suggests an additional ± 2 nmol/mol uncertainty. This extra uncertainty however mainly affects ozone measurements conducted in highly variable water vapour regimes (deep ascent/descent within free troposphere) and upper troposphere/lower stratosphere.

Note that the impact of differential pressure and water vapour on the 2B Technologies photometers equipped with Dewline Nafion water exchange membranes is a known issue, which has been addressed and reported by other airborne research groups (e.g. Hints et al, 2021).

References

Eric J. Hints et al, UAS Chromatograph for Atmospheric Trace Species (UCATS) – a versatile instrument for trace gas measurements on airborne platforms, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 14, 6795–6819, 2021 (doi.org/10.5194/amt-14-6795-2021)

